

ISic0190

I.Sicily inscription 0190

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Foun in the ruins of the castel at Termini Imerese, in 1886

Coordinates

37.988602, 13.697916

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 18 cm

Width 24 cm

Depth 9 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]P(ubli) l(iberto) Lesbi[o]

2. [---]l(iberto)Damoph[ilo]

3. [---]tas f(ecit) d(e) s(uo)

Apparatus

Text after ILTermini with slight changes based on the photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285319

EDR 127544

EDCS 10900656

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0190. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334488>